

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Start / Duration	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	15/04/2026	Version	1.0

Deliverable 9.2

Assessment of integrated physical, biogeochemical and LTL projections in T9.2.1

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Document History:

Release	Date	Reason for Change	Status	Distribution

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	15/04/2026	Version	1.0

1.0		Initial document, reviewed	Released	Internal
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To cite this document

Artioli, Y., Guihou, K., & Drozd, I., Belharet, M., Gutknecht, E., Perruche, C., Wathen M. (2026). NECCTON Assessment of integrated physical, biogeochemical and LTL projections in T9.2.1 (D9.2), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19469592>

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable summarises the activities implemented in T9.2.1 of the NECCTON project, aimed at producing ensembles of bias-corrected downscaled climate projections for three different Copernicus Marine Services (CMEMS) domains: the global ocean (GLO), the North-Western Shelf (NWS) and the Black Sea (BS).

This work had three main objectives:

- To expand CMEMS capability to produce projections of impacts of climate change in the low trophic levels (LTL) of ocean ecosystems
- To provide a series of new products needed to drive projections of impact of climate change on higher trophic levels in ocean ecosystems (T9.2.2)
- To support the subset of NECCTON case studies that focus on climate change

The deliverable presents the different approaches used to create the ensemble and highlights a summary of the trends for a selected number of variables that are relevant to NECCTON goals.

All projections indicate that the ocean will significantly warm up under the higher emissions scenarios. However, under the lower emissions scenario, the increase in surface temperature is projected to stabilize overall, in all domains. Differently, the trends of net primary production are remarkably different across domains. In the global domain, no clear trend is visible and net primary production oscillates around the historical values. In the NWS domain, all projections show a decreasing trend. In the Black sea, a weak positive trend is projected, which however does not compensate the drop in net primary production in the first years of the scenario. In all domains, the spatial patterns of climate change impact on primary production are highly variables, in both intensity but and direction. The full description and quantification of the impact of climate change on the LTL of the three regions is out of the scope of this deliverable and will be the focus of a series of publications that are currently in preparation.

The work implemented in T9.2.1 allowed for the development of working pipelines that will enable CMEMS to expand its product portfolio towards climate projections. It also allowed to review benefits and pitfalls of the different approaches of bias correction (e.g. limits in projecting changes in variability, constraints in scenarios selection) that will inform the development of the CMEMS protocols for climate projections as well as the wider scientific community active on this topic (e.g. the UN decade project FLAME).

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2. Scope of this deliverable

The scope of this deliverable is to illustrate the different approaches used to produce climate projections for the physics, biogeochemistry and low trophic levels of marine ecosystems and to assess the climatic trends in a selection of variables in three different domains of CMEMS: the global (GLO), the NorthWestern Shelf (NWS) and the Black Sea (BS).

The work has been carried out in task 9.2.1, coordinated by PML and implemented by MOi, PML and UoL. The simulations presented here will be then used to drive a series of high trophic level models in task 9.2.2 and to inform a selection of the NECCTON case studies, namely C5 (Climate-smart MPA planning in the North West European Shelf), C6 (Ensemble model evaluation and projection of small pelagics in the Bay of Biscay), and C12 (Monitoring marine mammals in the Azores region) and C13 (Forecasting climate change impact on potential catches of open ocean large pelagic fish).

This work is based on the same modelling systems that are at the core of D5.1, D5.2, D6.1, D6.2 and D9.1 and therefore most details about the formulation and parameterisation of the models are not included in the current deliverable.

3. Introduction

Among the multiple stressors that put marine ecosystems under pressure, climate change (warming and de-oxygenation) and ocean acidification are some of the more challenging ones. The temporal and spatial scale at which they act is generally much wider than most of the other stressors and therefore a deeper understanding on how they interact with the local pressure is needed. Their impact is already visible in all marine ecosystem components, from the physical environment (e.g. warming) to the chemical one (e.g. de-oxygenation and acidification) to the biological and ecological one (with significant contraction or displacement of habitat). Being able to project the impacts of these global stressors in marine ecosystem under different scenarios is paramount not only to understand the risk associated to a lack of implementation of climate mitigation actions, but also to assess their interaction with any other action put in place to mitigate the negative effect of other human activities. For instance, the impact of climate change alone is projected to decrease global fish biomass by 5-15% (Tittensor et al., 2021) with consequence not just on the fishery economic sectors, but also on all the measure implemented to contrast overfishing. Similarly, designing the network of MPAs using a climate-smart approach (Arafeh-Dalmau et al., 2023; Queirós et al., 2021) allow to guarantee their effectiveness in the long-term.

Usually, global coupled Earth System Models (ESMs) are used to assess the impact of climate change in our oceans. These models, at the basis of the IPCC Assessment Report on climate, are formidable

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tools to understand the role of the oceans in the climate system and how the oceans change in response to changes in climate. However, their primary goal is the representation of the climate system, and not to closely match all the complex details of the ocean reality. Therefore, the use of ESMs to assess impact comes with several limitations. For instance, ESMs can be affected by biases or by inaccuracies in reproducing the interannual variability of the ocean, for specific reasons including long, unconstrained spin-ups and protocols for the initialization of the ensembles (Liu et al., 2010). This, in turn, can affect their ability to properly reproduce the timing of past events or the passing of critical thresholds. Furthermore, their spatial resolution and their complexity is still sub-optimal to represent coastal seas where many social and economic interests lie. One way to address these problems is to downscale the ESMs with ocean-only models that are constrained by the ESMs. This approach is rigorously applied for the atmospheric projections through the WCRP initiative “Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment” (CORDEX – <https://cordex.org>). However, there is no globally coordinated activity for marine projections, and individual research activities have filled this gap where funding and opportunities were available (Copernicus Climate Change Service, 2020; Drenkard et al., 2021; Galli et al., 2024; Holt et al., 2025; Pozo Buil et al., 2021; Solidoro et al., 2022).

Recently, few international complementary efforts have been initiated to further develop the science behind regional dynamic downscaling of ocean climate projections and to coordinate the implementation of such activity. WCRP CLIVAR-OMDP and CORDEX have established a joint task force on Regional Ocean Climate Projections (<https://cordex.org/strategic-activities/taskforces/task-force-on-regional-ocean-climate-projections/>), the UN Decade for Ocean Science program Coast Predict has established the project Future Coastal Ocean Climates (FLAME – <https://noc.ac.uk/projects/flame>), and the EU has funded the project SEACLIM (<https://seaclim.eu/>). With its extensive modelling capability, CMEMS is perfectly placed to support these international efforts and to be a core provider of ocean climate projections that are tailored to support marine managers and practitioners to include climate change on their management and development plans. Task 9.2.1 of NECCON aimed at developing such capacity leveraging on the expertise of some partners involved in different CMEMS Monitor and Forecasting Centres (GLO, NWS and BS). For each of these domains, a small ensemble of 4 downscaled climate projections was implemented under two different SSP scenarios (a lower emission one and a higher emission) and using two CMIP6 models of different equilibrium climate sensitivity (ECS). ECS represents the intensity of warming following a doubling of atmospheric CO₂ (Meehl et al., 2020), and is an indicator of the intensity of warming that different ESMs project within the same SSP scenario. Using models of different ECS to constrain ocean climate projections allowed us to represent part of the uncertainty in the estimated impact of climate change.

For the GLO and NWS domains, we choose the scenarios SSP1-2.6 for the lower emissions scenario, and SSP3-7.0 for the higher emissions one, while the ESM were CNRM-ESM2-1 (Séférian et al., 2019) and GFDL-ESM4 (Dunne et al., 2020). Their ECS is respectively 4.8°C and 2.6°C (Meehl et al., 2020), making CNRM-ESM2-1 the most sensitive model and GFDL-ESM4 the less sensitive one in the CMIP6 ensemble. Due to the need for higher resolution atmospheric forcing of the Black Sea model, for the BS domain it was not possible to use the same scenarios or ESM, as the choice was limited by the

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availability of dynamically downscaled regional atmospheric projections that were available to the partner. As a consequence, the ensemble for the BS was built using the SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios and the MPI-ESM1-2-HR-EUR (Müller et al., 2018) and EC-Earth3-Veg (Döscher et al., 2022). The ECSs of these two models are 3.0°C and 4.3°C.

Glossary

Acronym	Meaning
AMM7	Atlantic Margin Model at 7 Km resolution
BS	Black Sea domain
CLIVAR	Climate and Ocean: Variability, Predictability and Change
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Services
CMIP6	6 th Coupled Model Intercomparison Program
CORDEX	Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment
DVM	Diel Vertical Migration
ERA5	5 th generation of European Reanalysis of the Atmosphere
ESM	Earth System Model
GLO	Global domain
HTL	Higher trophic level
INTNPP	Depth Integrated Net Primary Production
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LTL	Lower Trophic Level
NWS	NorthWestern Shelf domain
OMDP	Ocean Model Development Panel
PGW	Pseudo Global Warming
SSP	Shared Socio-Economic Pathways
SST	Sea Surface Temperature
WCRP	World Climate Research Programme

4. Global domain

Methods

Here we rely on the Pseudo Global Warming method (PGW) (Kawase et al., 2009; Kimura and Kitoh, 2006) to bias-corrected the atmospheric forcing from CMIP6 models so that our ocean projections are more realistic over the historical period, thus tailored to better force ocean ecosystem models: the trend of CMIP6 models (Eyring et al., 2016) and the ERA5 reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2020) are combined to project the changes of the atmospheric forcing of the ocean simulations, for various past and future scenarios.

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Figure 1: example of the implementation of the PGW method to the 2-m air temperature. The black lines show the ERA5 reanalysis and its trend, the blue thick lines the ERA5_CNRM corrected forcing, and the orange thick lines the ERA5_GFDL corrected forcing. The thin lines show the trends of the ensembles from the CMIP6 model before correction (blue for CNRM-ESM2-1 and orange for GFDL-ESM4). Dotted lines are for the historical period (1959-2014), dashed lines for the SSP1-2.6 scenario and solid lines for the SSP3-7.0 (2015-2087). Grey areas delimit the reference historical period (1995-2014) and the projected reference period (2060-2079), both with the same interannual variability.

The correction is applied to the 2-m air temperature, 2-m specific humidity, 10-m winds, downwards shortwave and longwave fluxes and precipitations (see figure 1 for the air temperature). For each of these variables, and at each grid point, the trend of ERA5 is removed. Then the trend of the mean of each CMIP6 ensemble is extracted and applied onto the detrended ERA5. Both historical forcings are fit onto the initial condition of ERA5 in 1959, thus ensuring a correction of the mean bias. The projections are also fitted so that the end of the historical period (December 2014) is aligned with the beginning of the projections (January 2015).

The ensemble of global oceanic projections uses the same parametrisation of the model PISCES as the global 1° hindcast from the T9.1. The reader can refer to D5.2 for a full description of the model. The climate simulations start in 1959 from a restart, obtained after a 64 years spinup using the detrended ERA5 forcing (Guihou et al., in prep). The spinup itself was initiated from a state at a quasi-equilibrium, coming from a twin experiment forced by the JRA-5 atmospheric forcing (Lengaigne et al., 2024). The simulation of the Diel Vertical Migration (DVM) in the PISCES model, implemented in NECCTON (see D5.2) has been activated after the spin-up. As a consequence, the first years of simulations of some biogeochemical variables can display an adjustment in the model, that is quickly absorbed. A similar ensemble without the DVM has also been produced, featuring the same physics, and the sensitivity of the projections to this parameter is currently being assessed, and is outside of the scope of this deliverable.

The list of simulations can be found in table 1. The ensemble includes 2 CMIP6 models (CNRM-ESM2-1 and GFDL-ESM4) and 2 scenarios (SSP1-2.6 and SSP3-7.0). Two historical simulations have been run from 1959, as well as a hindcast, to propose a longer reference run than the hindcast from T9.1. The

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projections start in 2025 and have run until 2087. The list of variables requested to perform the high tropic level models from T9.2.2 have been extracted onto a regular 1° grid and at a monthly resolution (tables 2 for the physics and 3 for the BGC). All data necessary for T9.2.2 (HTL projections) have been transferred to the partners, and files are going to be available in the NECCTON portal.

Results

This section presents results for a selected subset of variables, relevant to the NECCTON HTL models and use cases. A more detailed analysis of the simulations is planned and will be the focus of a scientific publication in preparation.

Sea Surface Temperature (SST)

Over the historical period, both members are very similar and close to the hindcast (figure 2), with mean biases of -0.02 and -0.06 °C for NP-ERA5-CNRM and NP-ERA5-GFDL, respectively. They both feature a warmer equatorial Pacific and Indian Ocean, as well as a cooler Northern Atlantic.

The projected SST from all members shows an increase in the future. As expected, SSP3-7.0 projects a warmer future than SSP1-2.6: the more optimistic scenario shows a stabilization of the SST from 2050 onwards, whereas the more pessimistic scenario shows a continuous warming until the end of the simulations. For both scenarios, the members forced by the corrected CNRM-ESM2-1 are warmer than the ones forced by the corrected GFDL-ESM4. This can be partly explained by a stronger cooling of the Northern Atlantic cold blob in NP_ERA5_GFDL, as well as a cooler Pacific.

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Figure 2: impact of climate change on sea surface temperature. The top plot shows the timeseries of the average value in the domain (SSP3-7.0 full lines, SSP1-2.6 dashed lines) and the maps show the bias between the historical simulations and the hindcast over the reference period (1995-2014), and the projected changes referred to their respective historical for the future reference period (2060-2087). Periods used in the maps are shaded in grey in the timeseries. Areas affected by sea-ice coverage have been masked white.

Integrated Primary Production

The integrated primary production (INTPP) interestingly shows no significant global mean projected trend (figure 3). The decrease of INTPP along the equatorial Pacific intensifies with the global warming, but it is balanced by an increase in the equatorial Atlantic and the Southern Ocean.

The model's choice has a small impact compared to the scenario choice. We observe local variations between SSP1-2.6 and SSP3-7.0, but both members of each scenarios have general similar patterns. The INTPP content in the ACC, in particular south of Australia, seems to be one of the few regions

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where the forcing model has a visible impact, along with the extension of the Pacific cold tongue. There is a revert in the sign of projected change of INTPP in the region of the Peruvian upwelling for NP_ERA5_CNRM, which is the only member to predict an increase of INTPP in this area.

Figure3: impact of climate change on integrated primary production. The top plot shows the timeseries of the average value in the domain (SSP3-7.0 full lines, SSP1-2.6 dashed lines) and the maps show the bias between the historical simulations and the hindcast over the reference period (1995-2014), and the projected changes referenced to their respective historical for the future reference period (2060-2087). Periods used in the maps are shaded in grey in the timeseries. Areas affected by sea-ice coverage have been masked white.

Mesozooplankton

The projected integrated mesozooplankton shows a negative trend (fig. 4), for all members of the ensemble, in the first part of the 21st century, then stabilizing around 0.38 mmol/m³. The NP-ERA5-

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GFDL model is slightly more productive, mainly explained by a positive trend in the Southern Atlantic. As already observed with PP, only NP-ERA5-CNRM SSP3-7.0 shows a positive trend in the region of the Peruvian upwelling.

Mesozooplankton is a NECCTON variable and will be made available through the NECCTON data portal.

Figure 4: impact of climate change on integrated mesozooplankton. The top plot shows the timeseries of the average value in the domain (SSP3-7.0 full lines, SSP1-2.6 dashed lines) and the maps show the bias between the historical simulations and the hindcast over the reference period (1995-2014), and the projected changes referenced to their respective historical for the future reference period (2060-2087). Periods used in the maps are shaded in grey in the timeseries. Areas affected by sea-ice coverage have been masked white.

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5. North-West Shelf domain

Methods

The regional climate change projections in the NWS domain have been obtained using the NEMO-ERSEM model implemented in the AMM7 domain, the same model system for the hindcast simulation described in D5.2. We refer to that document for most details about the model system and the configuration, and we will focus here only on the necessary change made to implement climate projections. The simulation started in 1993 and ended in 2100, with the period 1993-2014 describing the historical climate, and the period 2015-2100 the future climate. The historical simulations started in 1993 to align with the hindcast. Before starting the proper simulation, the model was spun up for 15 years simulating the period 1993-1997 for three times.

Differently than for the hindcast, the innovative light spectral module implemented in the NECCTON hindcast has not been used, and we reverted to the standard broadband module (Butenschön et al., 2016) using the “ady” passive tracer to take into account for the impact of detritus and organic matter on light absorption. The passive tracer is nudged at surface to the satellite derived product “ady” from (Sathyendranath et al., 2019). Because of the lack of information about future trends of such variable, we made a climatology of the product used for the hindcast and kept it constant throughout the entire simulation period.

ATMOSPHERIC FORCING

Atmospheric forcings were bias corrected using the PGW approach, similarly to what was used in the GLO domain. First, the ERA5 was interpolated on the grid of the CMIP6 atmospheric model. Then, the regridded ERA5 product was detrended and repeated several times to extend the time series until end of 2100. Linear trends for the historical period (1993-2014) and the future projection period (2015-2100) were calculated on a cell-by-cell basis for all variables from the annual mean values of the CMIP6 model. The historical linear trend was then applied to the detrended reanalysis period (1993-2014) preserving the long-term mean of the reanalysis to avoid introducing any bias. Then the linear trend of the projection period was applied to the remaining of the detrended reanalysis timeseries making sure of a seamless transition between the historical and future projection timeseries. Figure 5 illustrates the method for one timeseries of air temperature. This approach simplifies the real temporal evolution of climate by assuming a linear relation with time and also prevents to include any climate induced change in the short-term variability (e.g. interannual and seasonal). Different approaches of bias correction have been recently proposed (Pozo Buil et al., 2023), but they can dampen the interannual variability. Furthermore, the adoption of the simple PGW approach allowed for a full consistency with the GLO case study.

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Figure 5: example of the implementation of the delta method to bias correct air temperature. Dots show annual mean values from the CMIP6 model (blue historical and red scenario), and the dotted line their linear trends. The black line the annual mean from the ERA5 dataset and the blue and red lines show the resulting bias corrected annual means.

This approach was followed for all atmospheric variables except for short-wave radiation that was not bias corrected: imposing a long-term linear trend on this variable characterised by null values during nighttime would have led to significant impact on the duration of the diel cycle. Trends of short-wave radiation in the CMIP6 models were anyway modest and therefore the impact on the simulation has been deemed minimal.

LATERAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

Two slightly different approaches have been used for the open ocean lateral boundary condition and the Baltic Sea lateral boundary condition. This was necessary because the coarser resolution of the CMIP6 models does not allow for a good representation of the dynamics in the Skagerrak. For instance, in the CNRM-ESM2-1 model the connection between the Baltic Sea and the North Sea is represented by a channel of one grid cell in the T and V grids (i.e. for, T, S, ssh and northward velocity) and none on the U grid (eastward velocity).

For the open ocean lateral boundary condition, we used the same approach implemented for the atmospheric boundary conditions to both, physical and biogeochemical lateral boundary conditions with few adjustments. First of all, we extracted and regridded values from the CMIP6 models for the following variables: temperature (thetao), salinity (so), sea surface height (zos), velocities (uo, vo), nitrate (no3), phosphate (po4), silicate (si), oxygen (o2), dissolved inorganic carbon (dissic), total alkalinity (talk). This was done first implementing a bilinear interpolation on each z-level of the CMIP6 model, then a linear interpolation on the vertical.

Then, we bias corrected the CMIP6 derived physical lateral boundary conditions using the PGW approach described above using the hindcast lateral boundary condition as reference. For biogeochemical variables, we adopted the same approach, but estimating the relative trend from the CMIP6 models rather than the absolute trends. This is because the bias in biogeochemical

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variables can be very high (fig. 6), and therefore applying the absolute trend from CMIP to the hindcast lateral boundary condition could lead to unrealistic values (e.g. negative).

Figure 6: comparison of surface nitrate in a boundary point in the proximity of the North Atlantic gyre from CNRM-ESM2-1 and from WOA23.

For all other biogeochemical variables, we imposed the same boundary condition used in the hindcast.

For the Baltic Sea lateral boundary condition, we used a similar approach but rather than regridding the CMIP6 model on the AMM7 Skagerrak boundary points, the climatic linear trends were extracted from a single location in the CMIP6 model: data were first averaged on the vertical axis, then linear trends for the historical and future projection period were extracted and applied as for the open ocean lateral boundary condition.

RIVER FORCING

In order to include the impacts of climate change on the land-sea interaction, we have adopted an approach originally developed within the context of the EU funded project Mission Atlantic (Artioli et al., 2023) that combines information about changes in freshwater fluxes from the CMIP6 and changes in nutrient discharge from global catchment models.

CMIP6 ocean models provide timeseries for the freshwater fluxes from rivers (variable friver), however information about nutrients inputs are rarely available from CMIP6 data repositories and not all CMIP6 models include nutrient inputs from rivers (Séférian et al., 2019). Global/regional catchment models can provide both, however, unless the catchment model has been run using the same CMIP6 model as forcing, the projected changes in the freshwater fluxes would not be aligned to the changes in atmospheric climate used to drive the regional climate projection. For this reason, we have decided to use the CMIP6 outputs to derive the linear trends for freshwater fluxes, and outputs from the global catchment model IMAGE-GNP (Beusen et al., 2016) for the nutrient fluxes. We acknowledge that this approach decouples the trends in freshwater and nutrient fluxes from rivers, however we believe this is a preferable compromise than decoupling the freshwater fluxes

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from the atmospheric forcing (as this could affect the hydrodynamic of the regional projection) as well as keeping a fixed climatology for nutrient fluxes, as this would ignore any impact of socio-economic change.

To resolve the mismatch in resolution between the regional AMM7 model and the global models (CMIP6 and IMAGE-GNP), each of the river mouth locations in the AMM7 domain has been therefore mapped to a grid cell of the global model containing a valid value to determine which linear trend to apply. The mapping was first implemented automatically through a nearest neighbour approach on projected coordinates, followed by a manually check for the largest rivers to correct any potential mismatch due to different land-sea mask grids in the models.

Rather than applying the climatic linear trend to the detrended reanalysis, we decided to first calculate the climatology of the hindcast forcing. This was necessary because freshwater fluxes have a wide range of variability and can have very low value during period of draught. Imposing simple linear trends to a timeseries with such high variability could lead to negative values during draught (when the trend would impose lower than average fluxes). Using a climatological seasonal cycle allow to apply the PGW method avoiding these extreme conditions.

Atmospheric nitrogen deposition.

Similar than in the case for nutrients fluxes from rivers, only a limited amount of CMIP6 models provides data for atmospheric nitrogen deposition and therefore we used (Yang, Jia and Tian, Hanquin, 2022) as a source to calculate the trends. Because of a significant bias between the product used for the hindcast based on EMEP (Simpson et al., 2012) and the product used to calculate the trends, the relative trends have been used in the implementation of the bias-correction approach, as for the biogeochemical boundary conditions.

Results

Here we will briefly present the impact of climate change in a selected group of indicators relevant to climate and marine ecosystems. A more detailed analysis of the all the impact of climate change in the lower trophic level ecosystem is remanded to following analysis and scientific publications that will spin out from the work presented here.

The full 4D datasets of all NECCTON variables have been delivered to the NECCTON Ocean Viewer.

Sea surface temperature (SST)

Average SST is projected to increase of about 1.0 degrees in the scenario SSP3-7.0, while is projected to stabilise to historical values or even slightly decrease in SSP1-2.6 (fig. 7). In the scenario SSP3-7.0 the two models converge to very similar projection as average warming, in contrast with the different Equilibrium Climate Sensitivity (ECS) of the parent ESM. This is however the result of a very different spatial pattern, with NE-CNRM-ESM2-1 projecting a cooling in the North-Western part of the open ocean and a strong warming on the shelf, while NE-GFDL-ESM4 projecting a more

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homogenous and (slightly) milder warming. This is the consequence of CNRM-ESM2-1 projecting a stronger and larger warming hole in the North Atlantic compared to GFDL-ESM4. In contrast, in the scenario SSP1-2.6 the two projections differ significantly, with NE-CNRM-ESM2-1 showing again a mild cooling in the off-shelf region and a mild warming on-shelf, and NE-GFDL-ESM4 a generalised cooling across the entire domain.

Figure 7: impact of climate change on sea surface temperature in the NWS. The top plot shows the timeseries of the average value in the domain in all 4 scenarios (SSP3-7.0 full lines, SSP1-2.6 dashed lines) and the maps show the difference between the two periods highlighted in grey (2081-2100 vs. 1995-2014).

Surface nutrients

Surface nutrients (nitrate and phosphate) show a generic decrease in all four projections (fig. 8), with small differences on the average trends between the two SSP scenarios and a slightly bigger difference between the projections driven by the two ESMs. This can be easily explained by the fact that warmer waters are more stratified and therefore subjected to less winter mixing that leads to less nutrients in surface waters. However, there is little correlation between the intensity of warming and the decrease in surface nutrients, especially in the NE-GFDL-ESM4 SSP1-2.6 projection where a generic cooling of surface waters still leads to a decrease in surface nutrients.

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Despite nitrate and phosphate have a decreasing trend in all simulations, the NE-CNRM-ESM2-1 simulations show a decrease in nitrate stronger than the NE-GFDL-ESM4, while the opposite is true for phosphate. Localised increase in nutrients occurs in area affected by river discharge (e.g. the Dutch coastal area, the Armorican shelf). More in depth analysis is currently underway to fully explain these patterns.

Figure 8: impact of climate change on surface nitrate (left) and surface phosphate (right) in the NWS. The top plots show the timeseries of the average value in the domain in all 4 scenarios (SSP3-7.0 full lines, SSP1-2.6 dashed lines) and the maps show the difference between the two periods highlighted in grey (2081-2100 vs. 1995-2014).

Integrated Net Primary Production (INTPP)

INTPP shows a general decrease across the domain (fig. 9), following the decrease in surface nutrients. There are, however, some significant exceptions.

First, in both SSP3-7.0 projections there is an increase in net primary production along the Iberian Peninsula that then continues along the shelf break. This suggests a potential increase in the coastal upwelling in NW of the Iberian coast that is then advected anticlockwise following the circulation pattern. It is important to note, however, that surface nutrients do not seem to show the fingerprint of such increase in upwelling. More in-depth analysis will be implemented to fully understand this process.

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Second, there are other areas where INTPP slightly increases (e.g. southern coast of the North Sea, south of the Faroe Islands), likely due to the increase in warming that stimulates productivity.

Figure 9: impact of climate change on depth integrated net primary production in the NWS. The top plot shows the timeseries of the average value in the domain in all 4 scenarios (SSP3-7.0 full lines, SSP1-2.6 dashed lines) and the maps show the difference between the two periods highlighted in grey (2081-2100 vs. 1995-2014).

Mesozooplankton

Trends and spatial pattern for mesozooplankton follow quite closely those for net primary production (fig. 10).

Mesozooplankton is a NECCTON variable, and as such the full timeseries is in the process of being made available on the NECCTON data portal.

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Figure 10: impact of climate change on depth integrated mesozooplankton biomass in the NWS. The top plot shows the timeseries of the average value in the domain in all 4 scenarios (SSP3-7.0 full lines, SSP1-2.6 dashed lines) and the maps show the difference between the two periods highlighted in grey (2081-2100 vs. 1995-2014).

Dissolved Organic Carbon

On average the surface concentration of total dissolved organic carbon will stay constant or slightly increase (fig. 11), with the exception of the NE-GFDL-ESM4 SSP1-2.6 simulation where a clear decreasing trend is noticeable.

The spatial pattern of the differences between end of the century and the historical period shows a common structure: off-shelf there is a tendency to an increase in concentration in the Northern part (North of 50N) and a mild decrease on most of the shelf region, except for the southern North Sea where the concentration does not change much (NE-CNRM-ESM2-1) or increases (NE-GFDL-ESM4). The production and consumption of dissolved organic carbon is regulated by several process involving all trophic levels of the planktonic food web, and a more detailed analysis of the process driving this observed pattern will be carried out in the final year of the project.

Total dissolved organic carbon is a NECTON variable, and as such the full timeseries is in the process of being made available on the NECTON data portal.

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Figure 11: impact of climate change on surface dissolved organic carbon in the NWS. The top plot shows the timeseries of the average value in the domain in all 4 scenarios (SSP3-7.0 full lines, SSP1-2.6 dashed lines) and the maps show the difference between the two periods highlighted in grey (2081-2100 vs. 1995-2014).

Particulate Organic Carbon

Trends and spatial pattern for total particulate organic carbon mimic those of net primary production and mesozooplankton, with a much milder decrease projected on average and smaller areas where future concentration is projected to be higher than historical values (fig 12).

Total particulate organic carbon is a NECCTON variable, and as such the full timeseries is in the process of being made available on the NECCTON data portal.

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Figure 12: impact of climate change on surface particulate organic carbon in the NWS. The top plot shows the timeseries of the average value in the domain in all 4 scenarios (SSP3-7.0 full lines, SSP1-2.6 dashed lines) and the maps show the difference between the two periods highlighted in grey (2081-2100 vs. 1995-2014).

pH

Surface pH is the key indicator for ocean acidification, and directly respond to the partial pressure of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere, and therefore the big difference between scenario was fully expected, with SSP1-2.6 projections highlighting a stabilisation of the acidification trend to a level around -0.08 units, while both models project a constant acidification through time under the SSP3-7.0 scenario up to -.30 units (fig.13). The spatial pattern of acidification is not well visible in figure 13 but is considerable with the range between the 5th to 95th percentile of the order of 0.16 units in all projections, with the NE-CNRM-ESM2 projecting a slightly larger variability.

On shelf, bottom pH shows a similar pattern to surface pH, however sea floor acidification tends to be slightly stronger especially in the SPP3-7.0 scenario (-0.31 units). Range of variability of differences in bottom pH are smaller compared to those in surface pH (around 0.11 units in SSP1-2.6 and 0.12 units in SSP3-7.0), consistently with the smaller natural variability of bottom waters, especially in the area affected by seasonal stratification.

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Bottom pH is a NECCTON variable, and as such the full timeseries is in the process of being made available on the NECCTON data portal.

Figure 13: impact of climate change on surface pH (left) and bottom pH (right) in the NWS. The top plots show the timeseries of the average value in the domain in all 4 scenarios (SSP3-7.0 full lines, SSP1-2.6 dashed lines) and the maps show the difference between the two periods highlighted in grey (2081-2100 vs. 1995-2014). Only on-shelf data are considered for bottom pH.

Macrofauna

Trends and spatial patterns of benthic macrofauna (fig. 14) largely follow the patterns seen in net primary production with a generalised decrease in biomass in all projections, especially for suspension feeders. The decrease in SSP3-7.0 NE-CNRM-ESM2 projection is limited thanks to the stronger increase in biomass in the Armorican shelf, consequence of the stronger increase in net primary production in the region.

Macrofauna is a NECCTON variable, and as such the full timeseries is in the process of being made available on the NECCTON data portal.

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Figure 14: impact of climate change on biomass of suspension feeders (left) and deposit feeders (right) in the NWS. The top plots show the timeseries of the average value in the domain in all 4 scenarios (SSP3-7.0 full lines, SSP1-2.6 dashed lines) and the maps show the difference between the two periods highlighted in grey (2081-2100 vs. 1995-2014).

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6. Black Sea domain

Methods

Regional climate projections for the Black Sea were obtained using the NEMO ocean model (v4.2.0) (Madec et al., 2015) coupled with the BAMHBI biogeochemical model (v1.1) (Grégoire et al., 2026).

The simulations cover the period from 1 January 1950 to 1 January 2100. The initial five years (1950-1955) were used as a model spin-up. The period from 1955 to 2014 was considered the historical period, while the period from 2015 to 2100 represents the climate projections. The 60-year historical period was selected to assess potential model drift in long-term simulations and to account for it in the analysis of climate projections. All simulations were performed without data assimilation or statistical bias correction.

The physical parameters of the model were tuned through comparisons with ARGO profiles and Cold Layer Content diagnostics (Capet et al., 2020), ensuring realistic and stable temperature and salinity distributions in the upper 200 m.

The model domain has a horizontal resolution of approximately 15×15 km and includes 59 vertical z-levels. It covers the entire Black Sea basin, excluding the Azov Sea. The basin is treated as closed, except at the Bosphorus Strait, where water exchange is prescribed using an SSH-based inflow-outflow parameterization following Oguz et al. (1990) and Stanev and Beckers (1999).

Physical initial conditions were derived from temperature and salinity profiles averaged over the 1945-1955 period, based on the WOD dataset (Mishonov, 2024). Initial conditions for the BAMHBI model were constructed from density distribution functions of nutrients derived from Atlantis-II observations (Konovalov and Murray, 2001)

River forcing for the historical period was constructed from a combination of in situ measurements and data from the SESAME and EFAS datasets. For the future period, a river climatology based on daily data from 2000 to 2025 was applied (fig 15).

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Figure 15: The river forcing of freshwater runoff. The period 1950-2025 is based on measurement data, for the period 2025-2100 the 2000-2025 climatology is used.

Atmospheric deposition of nitrogen and phosphate was prescribed as spatially and temporally homogeneous, based on extrapolated in situ measurements (Koçak et al., 2016).

The atmospheric signal was introduced into the ocean model through surface forcing computed using the NCAR bulk algorithm (Large and Yeager, 2009). The methodology used to create the atmospheric forcing is described below.

Atmospheric forcing

The regional atmospheric model MAR (v3.14) was used to create high-resolution atmospheric forcing. The use of MAR allowed the preservation of large-scale climate signals from the driving CMIP6 models while improving the representation of regional processes specific to the Black Sea.

Boundary conditions for the MAR simulations were taken from CMIP6 global climate projections produced by the MPI-ESM1-2-HR-EUR (Müller et al., 2018) and EC-Earth3-Veg (Döscher et al., 2022) models under the SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios. Hereinafter, we will refer to these two ESMs as “MPI” and “ECE” respectively. The boundary conditions included zonal and meridional wind components, air temperature, and specific humidity. The historical period (1950-2015) and climate projections (2015-2100) were simulated with 10×10 km horizontal resolution using 24 sigma levels. The MAR simulations provided thermodynamically consistent atmospheric fields, including 2-m air temperature, 2-m dew point temperature, precipitation, cloud cover, shortwave and longwave radiation, as well as 10-m wind components.

The ECE and MPI atmospheric forcings show consistent large-scale trends in the evolution of atmospheric parameters over the Black Sea, but several important differences can be identified. The main differences between the two forcings are illustrated in figure 16.

Under the SSP5-8.5 scenario, both models project a substantial increase in 2-m air temperature by the end of the 21st century, reaching approximately $+3.5$ °C for MPI and $+5$ °C for ECE relative to the 1995–2015 mean. The SSP1-2.6 scenario also shows a warming trend in both models, although less pronounced, with increases of about $+1$ °C for MPI and $+1.75$ °C for ECE.

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A systematic difference in 10-m wind speed is also observed throughout the simulation period, with MPI forcing exhibiting, on average, wind speeds approximately 0.6 m s^{-1} higher than those in ECE. In addition, the ECE-based simulations indicate an intensification of precipitation toward the end of the 21st century under both scenarios, whereas this trend is not evident in the MPI-based simulations. No substantial differences were found for the remaining atmospheric variables.

Overall, the ECE forcing is characterized by higher near-surface air temperatures, lower wind speeds and intensification of precipitation compared to MPI forcing under both scenarios. These differences affect not only sea surface temperature, salinity, and circulation patterns, but also influence vertical mixing in the Black Sea by modifying stratification and buoyancy in the upper ocean layer.

Fig 16: The difference between MPI and ECE based atmospheric forcings in the air temperature at 2 m (top), wind speed at 10 m (middle) and precipitation (bottom). Full lines show SSP5-8.5, and dashed lines show SSP1-2.6.

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Results

Sea surface temperature (SST)

As shown in figure 17, SST in the Black Sea exhibits a clear long-term warming trend in all simulations, with an acceleration after the beginning of the projection period around 2015. Under the high-emission scenario SSP5-8.5, warming is substantially stronger, reaching approximately +3.25 °C with the MPI forcing and up to +4.75 °C with the ECE forcing by the end of the century relative to 1995-2014. In contrast, the SSP1-2.6 scenario results in more moderate warming, with increases of about +1 °C for MPI and around +1.75 °C for ECE. Spatial patterns of warming are relatively homogeneous across the basin, although slightly enhanced warming is visible in the central and eastern parts of the sea, particularly under SSP5-8.5.

ECE systematically produces higher SST than MPI throughout the simulation period, reflecting stronger atmospheric warming in this forcing. The differences between scenarios dominate over inter-model differences, but the choice of atmospheric forcing still leads to a spread of up to 1.5 °C in projected SST by the end of the century.

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Figure 17: Impact of climate change on sea surface temperature in the Black Sea. The top plot shows the timeseries of the average value in the domain in all 4 scenarios (SSP5-8.5 full lines, SSP1-2.6 dashed lines) and the maps show the difference between the last 20 years of the scenario (2081-2100) and the last 20 years of the historical period (1995-2014).

Integrated Net Primary Production (INTNPP)

Figure 18 shows that vertically INTNPP in the Black Sea exhibits pronounced long-term variability. Historical INTNPP fluctuations are closely linked to changes in nutrient runoffs from major rivers, primarily the Danube and Dnieper. In the future, INTNPP remains relatively stable, with only a slight increase toward the end of the century. This limited variability is largely due to the use of climatological river forcing, which constrains long-term changes in nutrient inputs.

Spatially, the response to climate change is heterogeneous, with INTNPP increasing in the northern part of the northwestern shelf and decreasing across of the remaining shelf area. Only minor changes

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are observed in the deep basin, reflecting the generally low biological productivity of deep part of the Black Sea.

Overall, changes in riverine nutrient runoffs remain the primary driver of INTNPP variability, while differences between scenarios and atmospheric forcing play a secondary role.

Figure 18: Impact of climate change on Net Primary Production in the Black Sea. The top plot shows the timeseries of the average value in the domain in all 4 scenarios (SSP5-8.5 full lines, SSP1-2.6 dashed lines) and the maps show the difference between the last 20 years of the scenario (2081-2100) and the last 20 years of the historical period (1995-2014).

Mesozooplankton and Microzooplankton

Figure 19 shows that both meso- and microzooplankton biomass in the Black Sea exhibit pronounced long-term variability during the historical period, broadly consistent with the changes observed in

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primary production. In the future period, both meso- and microzooplankton biomass remain relatively stable, with only minor trends and limited sensitivity to emission scenario or atmospheric forcing.

Spatially, the response to climate change is heterogeneous and closely follows the patterns observed for NPP. A decrease in mesozooplankton biomass is evident over most of the northwestern shelf and along the southern and western coastal regions, with stronger reductions under SSP5-8.5. In contrast, microzooplankton biomass shows a marked increase in the northern part of the northwestern shelf, while decreasing over the remaining shelf area and the open basin.

Figure 19: Impact of climate change on integrated meso- (left) and microzooplankton (right) biomass in the Black Sea. The top plot shows the timeseries of the average value in the domain in all 4 scenarios (SSP5-8.5 full lines, SSP1-2.6 dashed lines) and the maps show the difference between the last 20 years of the scenario (2081-2100) and the last 20 years of the historical period (1995-2014).

Particulate Organic Carbon

Figure 20 indicates that surface particulate organic carbon (POC) exhibits strong variability during the historical period, consistent with changes in primary production and nutrient inputs. POC remains comparatively stable in the future period. Spatially, the largest changes are concentrated over the northwestern shelf, where a pronounced decrease in POC is observed in all experiments, while the deep basin shows only weak changes. Differences between forcings and scenarios are relatively small compared to the overall signal, although slightly stronger decreases are evident under SSP5-8.5 and with ECE atmospheric forcing.

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Fig 20: Impact of climate change on surface Particulate Organic Carbon in the Black Sea. The top plot shows the timeseries of the average value in the domain in all 4 scenarios (SSP5-8.5 full lines, SSP1-2.6 dashed lines) and the maps show the difference between the last 20 years of the scenario (2081-2100) and the last 20 years of the historical period (1995-2014).

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7. Conclusions

The work presented in this deliverable demonstrated the CMEMS modelling systems improved during NECCON are mature to produce climate projections. Comparing the different methods used to implement the projections and the impact those has on the results, few comments to inform the further development of this product within CMEMS can be highlighted:

1. Bias correction is important when the projections are aimed at informing management decisions on the marine environment that goes beyond the climate system. Inheriting the bias of the parent CMIP6 model can have a significant impact on key environmental variables that are crucial to assess impact on marine ecosystem: for instance, a colder bias in the historical period implies a positive bias in oxygen that can affect projections of hypoxia and impact on fish and fishery. Furthermore, constraining the atmospheric forcing of the historical period close to those used for the hindcast allows for a smoother transition of the parameterisation of HTL model calibrated using the hindcast products to the climate projections in T9.2.2.
2. The method used to bias correct atmospheric forcing (and lateral boundary condition in case of regional models) is very important. The PGW method used in the GLO and NWS domain is simple to implement, does not imply high computational costs, and allows for a completely free choice of CMIP6 models to use to force the projection. At the same time, however, by extending the present-day short-term variability (inter-annual and seasonal) into the future, it prevents to fully assess the impact of climate change. CMIP6 models project indeed an increased interannual variability (Kwiatkowski and Orr, 2018; Shi et al., 2024), and the PGW method is not able to account for such increase in variability. Alternative methods have been suggested to include some of these changes (Pozo Buil et al., 2023), but there is no simple method that is currently recommended by the international community able to account for all changes (Holt et al., 2025). Alternatively, a full dynamic downscaling of the CMIP6 atmospheric forcing could be used, as it has been done here in the BLKSEA domain. While this would be the ideal method to use, as it would account for all changes and would provide better spatial resolution to drive regional models, it is significantly expensive, both in term of computational costs as well as in human resources, requiring expertise that goes beyond modelling of the marine environment. Due its cost, it would also limit the choice of scenarios or CMIP6 model that are available to the marine projection.
3. Both regional projections have shown how important is to project freshwater and nutrient fluxes from rivers. In the BLKSEA domain, for instance, the projected changes of primary and secondary production are tightly coupled to nutrients inputs, and this is likely to also be reflected in further changes in the HTL community. Unfortunately, CMIP6 models are still limited in how the land-sea transfer of nutrient and carbon is simulated, and therefore more work in collaboration with land and freshwater modellers is recommended.

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4. The importance of running ensemble of projections not only in terms of multiple scenarios but also using multiple CMIP6 models has been confirmed. The difference between projections of the same SSP scenario can be significant either in term of the temporal trend or in their spatial variability, and sometimes even higher than the difference across scenarios. Characterising this uncertainty and communicating it efficiently to the relevant stakeholders is key in order for them to be able to make informed decisions.

Several EU projects are currently working on improving the methodology for ocean climate projection to support decision makers and managers (e.g. SEACLIM, RIVIERADE) as well as other international activity like the WCRP CLIVAR-OMDP/CORDEX initiative and the FLAME project, therefore we would recommend that while CMEMS start developing pipeline and products specification for climate projections on the basis of the work developed in NECCTON, it engages with those initiatives to benefits from their outcomes.

Despite the limitations highlighted, the bias corrected projections produced in T9.2.1 will be undoubtedly useful to implement projections of changes in dynamics of fish and charismatic species (T9.2.2) as well as informing about changing of habitats that needs protection (e.g. C5).

The work implemented in T9.2.1 allowed for the development of working pipelines that will enable CMEMS to expand its product portfolio towards climate projections. It also allowed to review benefits and pitfalls of the different approaches of bias correction (e.g. limits in projecting changes in variability, constraints in scenarios selection) that will inform the development of the CMEMS protocols for climate projections as well as the wider scientific community active on this topic (e.g. the UN decade project FLAME).

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9. APPENDIX

Table A1: list of simulations for the global. NP stands for NEMO-PISCES; DVM stands for Diurnal Vertical Migration parameterisation; ERA5_CNRM (ERA5_GFDL) stands for the corrected atmospheric forcing, based on ERA5 reanalysis and CNRM-ESM2-1 (GFDL-ESM4) ensemble's trend

Simulation	Type	Period	Atmospheric forcing	Initial Condition	Period
NP_ERA5_DVM	Hindcast	1959-2023	ERA5 reanalysis	spinup	1959-2023
NP_ERA5_CNRM_historical_DVM	historical	1959-2014	ERA5_CNRM (corrected CNRM-ESM21)	spinup	1959-2014
NP_ERA5_GFDL_historical_DVM	historical	1959-2014	ERA5_GFDL (corrected GFDL-ESM4)	spinup	1959-2014
NP_ERA5_CNRM_ssp126_DVM	ssp126	2015-2087	ERA5_CNRM (corrected CNRM-ESM21)	NP_ERA5_CNRM_historical_DVM	2015-2087
NP_ERA5_GFDL_ssp126_DVM	ssp126	2015-2087	ERA5_GFDL (corrected GFDL-ESM4)	NP_ERA5_GFDL_historical_DVM	2015-2087
NP_ERA5_CNRM_ssp370_DVM	ssp370	2015-2087	ERA5_CNRM (corrected CNRM-ESM21)	NP_ERA5_CNRM_historical_DVM	2015-2087
NP_ERA5_GFDL_ssp370_DVM	ssp370	2015-2087	ERA5_GFDL (corrected GFDL-ESM4)	NP_ERA5_GFDL_historical_DVM	2015-2087

Table A2: list of the physics variables saved from the global domain.

Variable	Name	Filename	Unit	Comment
Seawater conservative temperature	thetao	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_thetao.nc	°C	
Sea surface temperature	tos	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_tos.nc	°C	
Sea Bottom Temperature	sbt	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_sbt.nc	°C	
Sea temperature at bottom	thetao	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_thetao_bottom.nc	°C	
Sea temperature averaged over the whole water column	thetao	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_thetao_mean_full.nc	°C	
Sea temperature averaged over 0-150	thetao	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_thetao_mean_150m.nc	°C	

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Heat content 0-300m	hc300	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_hc300.nc	J/m2	
Seawater salinity	so	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_so.nc	PSU	
Surface seawater salinity	sos	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_sos.nc	PSU	
Sea-ice area fraction	Siconc	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_siconc.nc	-	
Ocean mixed layer thickness defined by sigma theta	mldr10_1	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_mldr10_1.nc	m	
Sea floor depth below geoid	mbathy	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_mbathy.nc	m	
Vertical Indices of the bottom depth	mbkt	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_mbkt.nc	-	
Sea water x velocity	uo	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_uo.nc	m/s	
Sea water y velocity	vo	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_vo.nc	m/s	

Table A3: list of biogeochemical variables saved from for the global domain.

Variable	Name FABM	filename	Unit	Comment
Euphotic layer depth	Heup	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_Heup.nc	m	Not valid at high latitudes
diatoms carbon	PHY2	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_PHY2.nc	mmol/m3	
diatoms carbon integrated over the water column	PHY2	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_PHY2_integrated_full.nc	mmol/m2	
nanophytoplankton carbon	PHY	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_PHY.nc	mmol/m3	
nanophytoplankton carbon integrated over the water column	PHY	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_PHY_integrated_full.nc	mmol/m3	
Oxygen concentration	O2	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_O2.nc	mmol/m3	
Oxygen concentration at the bottom	O2	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_O2_bottom.nc	mmol/m3	
(Micro)Zooplankton Concentration	ZOO	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_ZOO.nc	mmol/m3	

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(Micro)Zooplankton Concentration integrated over water column	ZOO	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_ZOO_integrated_full.nc	mmol/m ²	
(Meso)Zooplankton Concentration	ZOO2	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_ZOO2.nc	mmol/m ³	Discontinuity in the Southern ocean in June and December
(Meso)Zooplankton Concentration integrated over water column	ZOO2	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_ZOO2_integrated_full.nc	mmol/m ²	
sediment organic carbon burial	sedC	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_sedC.nc	mol C/m ² /s	
sediment organic carbon bottom deposition	BotC	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_BotC.nc	mol C/m ² /s	
microzooplankton Quadratic mortality	ZOO_QUADMORT	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_ZOO_QUADMORT.nc	mmol/m ³	
microzooplankton Quadratic mortality integrated over the water column	ZOO_QUADMORT	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_ZOO_QUADMORT_integrated_full.nc	mmol/m ²	
mesozooplankton Quadratic mortality	ZOO2_QUADMORT	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_ZOO2_QUADMORT.nc	mmol/m ³	
mesozooplankton Quadratic mortality integrated over the water column	ZOO2_QUADMORT	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_ZOO2_QUADMORT_integrated_full.nc	mmol/m ²	
Export of carbon (poc + goc) at 100m	EPC100	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_ZOO2_EPC100.nc	mol C/m ² /s	

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carbonate pH	PH	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_PH.nc	-	
(Micro)Zooplankton Concentration	CHL	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_CHL.nc	mg/m3	
Vertically integrated PP by phyto	TPP	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_TPP.nc	mg/m3 /d	
PP by phyto	INTPP	MODEL_SSP_reg_1m_PERIOD_INTPP.nc	mg/m2 /d	